

practiced, and harvest was in late Dec.

Water depth was recorded weekly. SB were caught daily from 1800 to 2200 h in a light trap 200 m from the field. Each morning the catch was recorded. The first SB were trapped the 2d wk of Jul (see figure). Population increased rapidly between late Sep and late Oct, then declined. Every 2 wk, 10 plants were randomly collected and height, stem length, and number of internodes of the main shoot were recorded. At harvest, 140 plant samples were collected, and percent SB damage at different internodes of the main stem was recorded (see figure).

Almost no SB were trapped at early seedling growth when soil was dry. During early elongation (Jul-Sep), when almost all of the stems were submerged, SB infested few plants. Peak SB infestation was at preflowering. At harvest, damage was low in the 13th internode, but was substantially higher in the last 3 internodes (see figure).

Data on peak SB emergence reflect the period of maximum plant infestation. Also, SB infestation increases with decreasing water level. *ℳ*

Percent SB-damaged internodes (base to apex) of deep water rice plants at harvest and variations of light trap catch, water level, plant height, stem length, and number of internodes, West Bengal, India.

Stem borer infestation on hybrid rice

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Hybrid rice was released in China in 1978. Since then, striped stem borer (SSB) *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) and yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* damage has increased. SSB attacks rice in Hunan, Jiangxi, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, and Sichuan Provinces, and YSB damages rice in southern Jiangxi and Fujiang, and northern Guangdong.

In surveys at the HAAS farm beginning in 1978, we found that SSB populations in hybrid rice fields were 28 to 36% higher than in other rice fields and that there were 107 to 170% more egg masses. There are 7 to 17 times as many YSB egg mass as in other rice fields.

Survival rates of SSB larvae during 3 yr were 8, 18, and 19% higher on hybrid than on other rices, and YSB larvae survival was 13 to 20% higher. Larvae and pupae of SSB that fed on hybrid rice weighed 17 and 13% more than those collected from other rices. The mean weights over 2 yr of SSB pupae that fed on hybrid rice were 30 and 32% higher than the weights of those that fed on other rices. The first year, SSB females grown on hybrid rice produced 46 to 103 eggs/female; in the second and third years, they produced 46 to 82 more eggs/female than SSB females reared on other rices.

YSB larvae reared on hybrid rice weighed an average 63 mg. Those reared on other rices weighed an average 51 mg. YSB females produced an average 262 eggs/female on hybrid rice and 224 eggs/female on other rices. Over 4 yr, YSB hibernating on hybrid rice had 89,

23, 40, and 46% mortality vs 11, 9, 21, and 24% on other rices.

Most hybrid rice lines have large stems, heavy foliage, thick sheath, and long duration, which may favor SSB and YSB development. *ℳ*

The correct name of the African rice stem-boring Diopsidae (stalk-eyed fly)

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In the 1950s a stalk-eyed fly (Diopsidae) was identified as an important rice stem borer in Africa. The fly became known as *Diopsis thoracica* Westwood, 1837. Subsequently most authors wrote that *thoracica* was a junior synonym of *Diopsis macrophthalma* Dalman, 1817, which had *Diopsis longicornis*

Macquart, 1835, as a second junior synonym. Alternatively, some authors have claimed that *macrophthalma* was in fact a *Diasemopsis*, although all recent authors agreed on the synonym of *longicornis* and *thoracica*. In recent applied literature, both *macrophthalma* and *thoracica* have been used to indicate this stalk-eyed fly.

I have examined the *macrophthalma*, with the cooperation of the Stockholm Museum, and although the specimen was teneral and discolored it is unmistakably a *Diasemopsis*. The correct name of the African stem-boring stalk-eyed fly is *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart, 1835. Junior synonyms are *thoracica*

Westwood, 1837, and *phlogodes* Hendel, 1923. *Diopsis longicornis* is a common rice stem borer throughout Ethiopian Africa. Damage often is compensated for by the growing rice plants.

Other *Diopsidae* are mentioned as potentially important rice stem borers, among which is a stalk-eyed fly with apical wingspots. This fly has been identified as *Diopsis apicalis* Dalman, 1817, or *Diopsis tenuipes* Westwood, 1837. As part of a systematic revision of *Diopsis* with an apical wingspot, I have examined types of both species and find they are synonymous. However, about 10 *apicalis*-like *Diopsis* are found in rice in Africa. *Diopsis apicalis* (syn. *tenuipes*)

only occurs in West Africa, where it is the dominant *Diopsis* with an apical wingspot. In East, Central (up to Cameroon), and Southern Africa there is another, closely related, dominant *Diopsis* with an apical wingspot. This latter species and about eight other *Diopsis* with apical wingspots that occur in rice, maize, and other gramineous crops have yet to be described. Until I have published my revision of this group of *Diopsis*, it is best to refer to flies with apical wingspots as species belonging to the *apicalis*-complex. These flies are secondary stem borers, and lay eggs on shoots with deadhearts or other damage. \mathcal{J}

Seasonal stem borer (SB) population fluctuations in Mymensingh, Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, several SB species attack rice and cause economic damage. We studied seasonal SB population fluctuations around the BINA farm from Jan to Dec 1982. Each week, 50 rice hills of the test fields were randomly sampled and SB larvae were removed from infested tillers. Populations of different species were recorded (see table).

From Jul-Oct, *Scirpophaga incertulas* constituted 60 to 97% of the SB population. From Nov to May, *Chilo*

Population of three SB species in Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Mo	Percent of SB population		
	<i>S. incertulas</i>	<i>Chilo</i> sp.	<i>S. inferens</i>
Jan	25	56	19
Feb	4	85	11
Mar	2	71	21
Apr	21	19	60
May	20	61	19
Jun	—	—	—
Jul	79	21	0
Aug	60	38	2
Sep	97	0	3
Oct	76	24	0
Nov	9	62	29
Dec	21	56	17

polychrysa and *C. auricilia* constituted 19 to 85% of the population. The *Sesamia inferens* population always was low, but

increased from Nov to May, perhaps because wheat, an alternate host, is planted. \mathcal{J}

Changing populations of rice insect pests in Chhattisgarh, India

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Expanded irrigation, double-cropping,

and cultivation of N-responsive modern rices have changed insect populations in Chhattisgarh.

Populations of 12 common pests have not changed, but those of 10 are causing more damage (see table). \mathcal{J}

Status of rice pests in Chhattisgarh, India.^a

Insect	1960-70	1971-84
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guen.)	xx	xx
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stal.)	—	xx
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Dist.)	xxx	xxx
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Motsch.)	xxx	xxx
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horva th)	xxx	xxx
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (W.M.)	x	xxx
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walker)	x	xxx
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walker)	x	x
<i>Mythimna</i> spp.	xxx	xxx
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> (Guen.)	xx	xx
<i>Dichdispa armigera</i> (Oliv.)	xx	xx
<i>Pamara mathias</i> (F.)	x	x
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp.	x	x
<i>Baliothrips biformis</i> (Bagnall)	x	x
<i>Spodoptera</i> spp.	xx	xx
<i>Leptocorisa</i> spp.	x	x
<i>Irigonotylus doddi</i> (Dist.)	—	x
<i>Cymodema basicornis</i> (Motschulsky)	—	x
<i>Nanophyes</i> spp.	—	x
<i>Cryptocephalus ovulum</i> Suffrian	—	x
<i>C. sehestedtii</i> Fabricius	—	x
<i>Phyllotreta rhotonica</i> Quivivier	—	x

^a xxx = major pest causing severe damage, xx = minor pest causing occasionally heavy damage, x = minor pest; = not reported.